

First record of *Mycena juniperina* from Turkey on a new host

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Abstract. *Mycena juniperina* (*Mycena* section *Supinae*) which was described by Aronsen was collected in Turkey on bark of *Juniperus excelsa*. It is characterized by small pileus, globose and amyloid spores.

Keywords: *Mycena juniperina*, new record, Turkey

Introduction

Mycena juniperina Aronsen is a member of the section *Supinae* Konr. & Maubl., which consists of seven species in Europe (*M. conicoalba* M. Villarreal & Esteve-Rav., *M. cupressina* Antonín & Maas Geest., *M. meliigena* (Berk. & Cooke) Sacc., *M. pseudocorticola* Kühner, *M. supina* (Fr. : Fr.) Quél., and *M. venustula* Quél.). *Mycena juniperina* can be distinguished from the other members of this section by the colour of pileus and its growth on juniper. Its microscopic features display resemblance to the widely-distributed European species *M. meliigena* and *M. pseudocorticola*. Among all the differences between these two species and *M. juniperina*, the following could be noted: both of them grow exclusively on bark of deciduous trees, while *M. juniperina* grows on coniferous trees; in addition, they possess different colours in both the stipe and pileus. Another species, *M. cupressina*, recently described from Italy (Antonín & Maas Geesteranus 1998), has a similar ochraceous coloured basidioma but it differs from *M. juniperina* by the smooth hyphae of the stipitipellis and by its habitat, *Cupressus sempervirens* L.

Mycena juniperina, collected on bark of *Juniperus communis* L. from two localities in southeast Norway, was proposed as a new species belonging to the section *Supinae* (Aronsen 1996).

In the type locality, it was described as a common species (Aronsen 1996), and later it was also reported from Sweden (Kummer & Miersch 2001; Læssøe 2005), Italy (Robich 2003), and Denmark (Læssøe 2005) (Fig. 1).

In Turkey, *Mycena juniperina* was collected on bark of *Juniperus excelsa* which is a new host for the fungus.

Fig. 1. Map of distribution of *Mycena juniperina* Aronsen

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Materials and Methods

The species was identified according to Moser (1983), Maas Geesteranus (1992), Rexer (1994), and Aronsen's key available at <http://home.online.no/~araronsen/mycenapage/mycenapage.html>. A part of the collection was sent to A. Aronsen for a critical review and confirmation. All materials are kept in the Mushroom Application and Research Centre of Selcuk University, Turkey.

Results and Discussion

Mycena juniperina Aronsen, Persoonia 16(2): 257-259 (1996).

Pileus 2.5-8 mm across, hemispherical to parabolic, finally convex, occasionally somewhat depressed in the centre or with a small papilla, conspicuously sulcate, pruinose to white-puberulous or even somewhat flocculose, pale brown or yellowish brown, often darker in the centre, with the margin paler to white (Fig. 2). **Flesh** very thin, whitish. **Smell** not distinct or somewhat acidulous. **Taste** mild, not distinct. **Lamellae** (7-) 10-12 reaching the stipe, fairly broad, somewhat ascending or arcuate to subhorizontal, the edge concave to convex, broadly adnate with a decurrent tooth, sometimes decurrent far down the stipe, pale yellowish grey or beige with the edge white-pruinose. **Stipe** 3-5 × ca 0.5

mm, equal or somewhat widened below the lamellae, and sometimes also towards the base, terete, curved, cartilaginous, fistulose, pruinose to puberulous, beige to pale brown, the base attached to the substratum with a patch of radiating, fine whitish fibrils. **Basidia** ca 28 × 14 μm, clavate, 2- and 4-spored, clamped. **Spores** 8-9.2 × 7.5-9 μm, globose, smooth, amyloid. **Cheilocystidia** 21-30 × 8-12 μm, forming a sterile band (lamellar edge homogeneous), clavate, covered with unevenly spaced, simple to branched, curved to straight excrescences, clamped. **Pleurocystidia** not detected. **Hyphae** of the pileipellis diverticulate. Hyphae of the cortical layer of the stipe covered with cylindrical excrescences, clamped, densely covered with caulocystidia, clavate, variously diverticulate (Fig. 3).

Specimen examined: **TURKEY:** Muğla – Fethiye, Babadağ, on bark of living *Juniperus excelsa* M. Bieb., alt. 1200 m, 5 May 2003, Doğan (1290).

The material was collected in the southern Mediterranean part of Turkey. The forest consists mainly of *Cedrus libani* A. Rich., mixed with *Abies cilicica* (Ant. & Kotschy) Carrière subsp. *cilicica*, *Quercus coccifera* L., and *Phillyrea media* L., although in some places, there are pure juniper forests (*Juniperus excelsa* and *J. foetidissima* Willd.).

In our specimen, cheilocystidia differs from the type by having shorter excrescences and smaller spores (probably unripe). From *Mycena cupressina* it differs by the diverticulate hyphae of the stipitipellis.

Fig. 2. *Mycena juniperina* Aronsen. Scale bar: 1 cm

Fig. 3. *Mycena juniperina* Aronsen: a – cheilocystidia, b – hyphae of the cortical layer of the stipe, c – caulocystidia, d – spores. Scale bar: 10 μm. Drawings: A. Aronsen

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